

To Study Co-morbidities as a Risk Factor for Mortality Associated with COVID-19: A Retrospective Cohort Study

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Abstract

Background: Comorbidities have been linked to higher in-hospital complications and fatality rates in individuals with COVID-19.

Aims and Objectives: We aimed to examine the body of research on the effects of COVID-19 and comorbidities on health and the economy, particularly as they relate to emerging nations like India.

Materials and Methods: Database of Covid -19 patients was assessed. It is a record based retrospective cohort study. The information used in this study is anonymous and covers only age and gender data.

Results: In present study, most common co morbidity was hypertension in which 43.80% patients were discharged and death in 31.80% patients. Most common double co morbidity was hypertension+diabetes in which 72.70% patients were discharged and death in 72.70% patients and the most common triple co morbidity was hypertension+diabetes+heart disease in which 58.70% patients were discharged and death in 58.10% patients.

Conclusion: Low-income nations with limited resources and an average socioeconomic background need to implement stringent policies for reasonably priced testing programs to locate, evaluate, diagnose, and quarantine asymptomatic individuals at home.

Keywords: COVID-19, Comorbidity, Hypertension, Diabetes, Mortality.

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Introduction

Novel Corona virus disease (COVID-19) has emerged as a serious public health problem worldwide.[1] COVID-19 has emerged as a pandemic and has taken over 1,431,513 lives (till Nov. 27, 2020) worldwide involving 191 countries.[1] More than 1,35,715 deaths (till Nov. 27, 2020) have been reported from India. Out of these 4,710 deaths (till Nov. 27, 2020) have been reported from Punjab.[2] Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) is a worldwide pandemic that started in Wuhan, China, and spread extremely quickly, making its way to other countries.

Most patients with COVID-19 have comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and chronic liver disease.[3] Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) patients or people with any other respiratory illnesses are also at higher risk for severe illness from COVID-19 [2].

Patients with comorbidities should take all necessary precautions to avoid getting infected with SARS CoV-2, as they usually have the worst prognosis.[4] Many of the poorer outcomes for COVID-19 have been related to cardiovascular comorbid. However, this may be due to the direct result of the cardiovascular condition itself or attributed to other comorbidities along with a cardiovascular condition.[5]

In this study, we have investigated the associations between comorbidities like hypertension, diabetes, chronic kidney disease (CKD) etc. as risk factors for COVID-19-related mortality in patients admitted to isolation MCH Rajindra hospital Patiala between Months July to November 2020. Whether and how much the comorbidities impact the outcome of mortality has not been yet clearly established. The aim of this study was to integrate recent advances and present an updated analysis of the relationships between comorbidities and

mortality as fatal outcomes associated with COVID-19.

Material and Methods

Study Site: This study was conducted in Government Medical College and Rajindra hospital Patiala. The records of patients admitted to isolation MCH building of Rajindra hospital Patiala between Months July to November 2020 were assessed for this study.

Study Design: For the COVID-19 cohort in this study, database of Covid -19 patients was assessed. It is a record based retrospective cohort study. The information used in this study is anonymous and covers only age and gender data. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Sample Size: Sample size for single comorbidity was data of 505 patients. Out of which 176 died and 329 recovered and discharged from the hospital. Sample size for various variables analysis differed by ± 25 because of some missing values in the database.

Statistical Analysis: Continuous variables were described using mean ± standard deviation and categorical variables were presented as frequency rates and percentages. The two-sided p value of

<0.05 was considered statistically significant and p value of <0.01 was considered as statistically highly significant. The data was subjected to statistical analysis using JASP software 0.14 version of the license.

Results

Patient Disposition: A total of database of 848 COVID-19 positive patients having comorbidities who were hospitalized between July 1 and Nov 30, 2020, was screened for inclusion in this retrospective cohort study. Out of this, data 528 patients had death as the outcome and 320 patients were recovered and discharged from the hospital. Data of 6 indoor COVID-19 positive patients with comorbidities was excluded due to various reasons of, referral to other hospital, brought dead and missing values of the variables. Data of total of 842 patients hospitalized for COVID -19 was included in the analysis in this study. Out of this data of 842, COVID-19 positive patients with single comorbidity were 505 with outcome as death (n=176) and discharged (n=329), 260 COVID-19 positive patients with double comorbidity with outcome as death (n=150) and discharged (n=110) and COVID-19 positive patients with triple comorbidity were 77 with outcome as death (n=31) and discharged (n=46) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Database showing comorbidities in study population

In present study, among the single co morbidities werehypertension, in which 43.80% patients were discharged and death in 31.80% patients, in diabetes, 42.80% were discharged and death in 50%, in heart disease, 7.60% were discharged and death in 6.80%, in chronic kidney and lung disease, 2.40% were discharged and death in 5.70% (Figure2).

Figure 2: Patients with single comorbidity

In present study, most common double co morbidity was hypertension+diabetes in which 72.70% patients were discharged and death in 72.70% patients, in hypertension+heart disease 9.30% patients were discharged and death in 5.50% patients, in hypertension+kidney disease 8% patients were discharged and death in 4.50% patients, in diabetes+heart disease 4% patients were discharged and death in 8.20% patients, in diabetes+kidney disease 3.30% patients were discharged and death in 5.50% patients. (Figure3).

Figure 3: Patients with double comorbidity

In presentstudy, most common triple co morbidity was hypertension+diabetes+heart disease in which 58.70% patients were discharged and death in 58.10% patients, in hypertension+diabetes+kidney disease in which 37% patients were discharged and death in 29% patients, in hypertension+diabetes+ lung disease in which 4.30% patients were discharged and death in 3.20% patients (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Patients with triple comorbidity

Discussion

This study showed co morbidities associated with covid 19 infection and number of patients died with these co morbidities and number of discharged patients. And the most common co morbidity found in this study was diabetes followed by hypertension. Dysregulated immunoresponse found in diabetic patients plays an important role in aggravating severity. DM is associated with mortality and morbidity in COVID-19 patients. Chronic conditions like obesity, cardiovascular disorders, and hypertension, along with changed expression of ACE2, dysregulated immunoresponse, and endothelial dysfunction can cause severity in covid infection.[6]

Despite having a large number of COVID19 patients, there are only few large, published studies are currently available with regard to the prevalence of comorbidities in patients with COVID-19 from India. A retrospective study of 522 patients with COVID-19 from a large medical college and hospital of Jaipur, India, reported presence of comorbidities in which, hypertension (42.5%), diabetes (39.7%), past history of tuberculosis (20.5%), COPD/Asthma (16.4%), CAD and CKD (13.7%) represent the common comorbidities.[7] Several concomitant risk factors associated with COVID-19 are CVD, hypertension, cancer, prior stroke, chronic lung disease, and chronic kidney disease. Among these, hypertension was found to be more present in the diabetic group of COVID-19 patients. Poorly controlled diabetes increases the risk for skin, bone, eye, ear, gastrointestinal, urinary tract, and respiratory infections, among others, with significantly increased hospitalization and mortality rates including covid infection.[8]

The virus is known to initiate diabetes by increasing the insulin resistance or by aiming at the pancreatic islets. ACE2 can serve as a therapeutic target and helping in microcirculation in the islets. Hypoxia, pulmonary distress after SARS-CoV2 infection may hinder the anti-coagulating action of the endothelium by promoting thrombosis.[9] In a study by Zhang JJ et al showed that hyper-tension (30.0%) and diabetes mellitus (12.1%) were the most common comorbidities with covid positive patients followed by chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in 1.4% patients.[10] In another study done by Jakhmola S et al which showed the data of hospitalized COVID-19 patients with comorbidity as a consequence of the disease, along with the death reports collected from various countries. The major co morbidity found was heart diseases including, cardiovascular diseases which were higher in hospitalized patients in Italy (77%), Sweden (54%), and Spain (53%). Followed by deaths due to hypertension was higher in Italy(69%) and France(26%). Death in diabetic

patients was more in Italy (32%) and France (31%). Deaths due to lung diseases associated with covid 19 were significantly higher in Netherlands (24%) compared to those hospitalized in countries like Italy (23%), Spain (17%), France (23%), and Sweden (17%). Moreover, deaths due to kidney diseases (21%) and neurological ailments (15%) were more in Italy. Also, immunodeficiency seems to have no effect with respect to mortality on the hospitalized patients of Sweden (5%). Deaths due to Liver diseases was higher in Italy (4%) and are least affected by SARS-CoV2 infection compared to other comorbidities under investigation.[11]

In a study done by Yang Xet al in covid positive patients showed most common co morbidity associated was acute respiratory distress syndrome (45%) followed by diabetes (35%) and liver dysfunction(30%) and death in acute respiratory distress syndrome (81%) followed by diabetes (34%) and liver dysfunction(28%).[12] Due to interference in gas exchange, covid associated pneumonia in heart patients may develop hypoxemia.[13] The viral particles are seen in the endothelial lining of glomerular capillary loops in electron microscopy. These findings strengthen the association of COVID-19 with kidney disorders underlying endothelial function in it.[14]

In another study done by Sanyaolu A et al in 2020 on COVID-19 comorbidities, had a total of 1786 patients, of which 1044 were male and 742 were female with a mean age of 41 years old. The most common comorbidities recognised in these patients were hypertension (15.8%), cardiovascular and cerebrovascular conditions (11.7%), and diabetes (9.4%). The less common comorbidities were coexisting infection with HIV and hepatitis B (1.5%), malignancy (1.5%), respiratory illnesses (1.4%), renal disorders (0.8%), and immunodeficiencies (0.01%). The majority of these patients (68%) were discharged, 17% remained hospitalized, 10% ended up in the ICU, and 15% ended in death.[15]

In another study by Bajgain KT et al in 2021 from major epicenters showing comorbidities in population from different countries showed that 42.3% patients were without any chronic comorbid condition, while 57.7% had one or more comorbidity. Major comorbidities were HTN (27.4%), Diabetes (17.4%), CVD (8.9%), COPD (7.5%), Cancer (3.5%), CKD (2.6%), and other (15.5%). Further, comorbidity distribution within the comorbid population group (N = 13,050) were CVD (10.7%), HTN (33.1%), Diabetes (21%), COPD (9.1%), Cancer (3%), CKD (4.3%), and other (18.8%). Hypertension followed by diabetes were the most common comorbidities seen in COVID-19 positive patients. It was seen that country specific major comorbidities also had HTN as one of the most common comorbidities

throughout all groups. And hypertension was most commonly seen in China (39.5%), Italy (35.9%), United States (38.9%), United Kingdom (27.8%), Iran with Diabetes (35%) South Korea with CVD (25.6%). Diabetes was the second most common comorbidity.[16]

In a study done by Khan MM et al in 2020 showed 41 studies comprising of 27 670 samples. The most common pre-existing comorbidities in COVID-19 patients were hypertension (39.5%), diabetes (25.2%) and cardiovascular disease (12.4%). The deaths were most common in patients who had pre-existing cardiovascular diseases, immune and metabolic disorders, respiratory diseases, cerebrovascular diseases, any types of cancers, renal, and liver diseases.[17]

In study done by Jindal Ret al showing 34 studies with 23,034 patients. The most common comorbidities in COVID 19 patients was 18.1% for hypertension, 17.7% for diabetes, 7.9% for hypothyroidism and 7.7% for cardiovascular diseases. For chronic kidney disease (CKD), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), cerebrovascular diseases, asthma, chronic liver disease, tuberculosis and cancer, the pooled prevalence was less than 4%.[18] In study done by Yang J et al showing eight studies including 46248 infected patients. The result showed the most prevalent clinical symptom was fever, followed by cough, fatigue and dyspnea. The most prevalent comorbidity were hypertension and diabetes, followed by cardiovascular diseases and respiratory system disease.[19]

In a study done by Alkhatami MG et al showing prevalence of lung comorbidities including asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung cancer was 3%, 2.2%, and 2.1% respectively. Mortality rates associated with these comorbidities was 30% (41/137) for COPD and 19% (7/37) for lung cancer respectively. No mortality rates were reported for patients with asthma. This study offers latest evidence of prevalence of chronic lung conditions among patients with COVID-19. Asthma, followed by COPD and lung cancer, was the most common lung comorbidity associated with COVID-19, while the higher mortality rate was found in COPD. Future studies are needed to assess other lung comorbidities and associated mortality among patients diagnosed with COVID-19.[20]

In study done by Singh AK et al showed result of eighteen studies with a total of 14 558 patients with most common comorbidity were 22.9% for hypertension, 11.5% for diabetes, and 9.7% for cardiovascular disease (CVD). Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), chronic kidney disease (CKD), cerebrovascular disease and cancer were less than 4%.[21] In another study by Khateri Set al

in 2020 showed prevalence of acute respiratory injury in patients with COVID-19 was estimated as 34%. Also, the prevalence of co morbidities found were acute respiratory distress syndrome (23%), acute kidney injury(10%), acute liver injury(19%), and shock(12%).[22]

Conclusion

The results of this study should help in identifying those individuals most at risk of severe complications from COVID-19, and hence it is useful for public health messaging on social distancing and self-isolation. This study helped understanding the association between comorbidities and COVID-19 as its presence associated with a poor outcome in patients with COVID-19. However, there are relatively less published research on comorbidities and associated outcomes from India. It is advisable that developing countries such as India with medical infrastructure having less resources and an average socio-economic background, must adopt a strict policy for manufacturing affordable testing programs to trace, test, identify asymptomatic cases. It was also seen that universal masking is associated with a significantly lower rate of COVID-19 infection. This clearly accentuate the importance of social distancing and mandatory use of masks. The policymakers should give clear guidance to those groups which are at an increased risk of severe COVID-19. The high mortality associated with COVID-19 and associated comorbidities demands for stressing on future preventative therapies, in addition to traditional risk prevention. In conclusion, this study indicates that the presence of co-morbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, CVD and COPD in individuals with COVID-19 is associated with increased risk of developing severe symptoms and mortality.

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